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Silicate refractory brick waste as quartz sand filler replacement in MOC-based composites

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the design and development of environmentally sustainable construction composites with an accent on the utilization of secondary raw material sources or wastes, whose secondary purpose was not discovered yet and are landfilled or downcycled only. This approach leads to a significant reduction in the environmental burden resulting from activities related to the construction industry and thus ensures its sustainability. Spent refractories are a potential candidate for this purpose. The presented experiment deals with the replacement of standard quartz sand filler by silicate refractory brick waste (SW) in magnesium oxychloride- (MOC-) based composite materials. The standard filler was replaced either partially, fully, or in excess in order to fully uncover the potential of SW as a filler in construction composites. As a matrix, MOC phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which is considered an eco-friendly alternative to Portland cement, was used, as it is known to be able to contain large amounts of filler of various origins. This way, three types of construction utilizing a waste material, which would otherwise end up landfilled, were prepared. To assess the effect of the filler replacement, a reference MOC-based composite using quartz sand as the only filler was prepared. In the SW-filled composites, the replacement ratio was 50, 100, and 150 % by weight. The introduction of SW caused an increase in compressive strength for all of the prepared samples, most significantly for composite SW50, in which the quartz sand was replaced by 50 wt%. The compressive strength of this composite reached a mean value of 101.30 MPa, which is 25 % higher than the reference composite. This value exceeds the lower compressive strength limit for a construction composite to work as a high-performance concrete by more than 20 MPa. Furthermore, all of the prepared composites show very high flexural strength values (over 30 MPa). The microstructural analysis also proved that the presence of capillary pores with a diameter range between 100 and 1000 nm, which are generally responsible for the water-induced damage in MOC-based composites was significantly decreased with the replacement of quartz sand by SW in the amount of 50 wt%.

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1. Introduction

The non-negotiable impact of industry on the environment motivates the research of many scientists nowadays. In the construction sector, the environment-related issues are quite pressing, as the production of Portland cement (PC) generates 0.55 tons of carbon dioxide, and an additional 0.39 tons are produced as fuel combustion emissions during the energy-production process, making the overall PC contribution equal to 7 % of total global carbon dioxide emissions[1,2]. Among the approaches with the potential to mitigate the contribution of the construction sector to the climate crisis, the utilization of spent and waste materials poses an option of interest[3,4]. This approach can ensure the increased environmental sustainability of the produced construction composite, as well as avoidance of economic difficulties connected with the use of pure raw materials, as end-of-life materials, which would otherwise end up landfilled are used. Wastes, spent materials, and industrial by-products were studied for use in the sustainable and greener production of building materials. For example, the use of waste clay brick powder (CBP) for low-carbon cement, concrete, and alkali-activated composites was extensively explored. The use of CBP in concrete helps to reduce CO₂ emissions and energy consumption, thus providing an excellent environmental benefit[5–9]. Based on waste processing and treatment, construction and demolition waste was investigated both as an alternative to natural fine and coarse aggregate and as a cement substitute[10–13]. Recently, recycled concrete aggregate was applied in the 3D printing of Portland-based cementitious materials[14]. Plastic, rubber, slag, and waste glass were also tested as waste-based aggregates for concrete and eco-friendly asphalt mixtures[15–19].

Spent refractories also pose as a potential candidate for natural aggregate replacement. The worldwide annual production of refractories reaches the amount of 35–40 million tons, while approximately 28 million tons of spent refractories are produced each year [20]. Generally, spent refractories are used in the steel-making or refractory production field as slag formers, slag conditioners, or partial substitutes for fresh raw materials[21–23]. The reuse of spent refractories mainly depends on their previous use, which has a direct effect on their composition and material possibilities, and moreover, the possible leachability of potentially toxic elements. Furthermore, the efficiency of their reuse is limited by the efficiency of the recycling process itself[24].

Silica refractories are usually produced in the form of shaped elements, such as bricks, from quartz sand. Silica refractory bricks generally contain over 94 % of silica[25]. The content of silica in the refractory mixture is closely related to the properties of the final refractory, and it is also a cause of the acidity of the material[26]. Silica bricks are generally used as a material for kiln roofs and walls in coke ovens, blast, open-arc or open-hearth furnaces, and soaking pits[27,28]. Concerning the properties of silica refractory bricks, they possess excellent thermal shock resistance, high abrasion resistance, and high chemical resistance, especially toward principal steel furnace fluxes (iron oxide, acid slags, lime)[29]. Their physicochemical properties can be further improved by the incorporation of nanometal oxides (nanosized titania, silica, zirconia, or magnesia)[30–32]. During the production process, which includes high-temperature processing, the original crystalline quartz phase transforms to other silica crystalline modifications, such as cristobalite, or tridymite, and also into glass silica phase. These phases are present in various ratios depending on the presence of additives impurities, which influence the behaviour of the silica phase during heating[33,34].

Due to their specific properties, refractory brick production waste as well as end-of-life refractories pose as a possible candidate for incorporation in construction composites in various manners. Berdnikova et al. studied the possibility of the synthesis of silicate binder from silica refractory brick waste through a low-temperature synthesis process, and its subsequent use in building materials. The developed materials showed high values of mechanical parameters comparable to those of commercially available construction composites[35]. Zeghad et al. studied the potential of refractory brick waste as a supplementary cementitious material in concrete. In their work, three types of refractory bricks were used in a PC-based matrix along with fine sand aggregate, polypropylene fibres, and polycarboxylate superplasticizer, forming ultra-high-performance concrete with compressive strength values revolving between 80 and 120 MPa[36]. Incorporation of refractory brick waste as an aggregate in cement-based composites was studied by Khattab et al. This study dealt with the introduction of both fine and coarse refractory waste brick aggregate in a PC-based matrix. It was shown that the combination of the two types of aggregate helped to improve the compressive strength, porosity, water resistance, density, and ultrasonic pulse velocity[37]. The behaviour of recycled refractory brick aggregate concrete was also studied by Nematzadeh et al., especially in terms of residual properties after exposure to elevated temperatures between 110 and 1000 °C. As a matrix, either PC or aluminate cement was used. The obtained results showed the deterioration of the mechanical properties of ordinary PC-based concrete at 400 °C and those of aluminate cement-based concrete at 110 °C[38].

To fully unravel the eco-friendly potential of construction composite, not only the alternative filler, in this case, refractory silica brick waste, but also the matrix should provide as high environmental sustainability as possible. In this regard, magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) is considered such alternative to the ordinarily used PC[39]. Its eco-friendly nature is even more enhanced by its ability to contain large amounts of waste materials as standard sand filler replacement. Among the researched waste materials, waste wood, straw, sawdust, waste plastics, glass, plasma gasification waste, or various types of sludge were incorporated in MOC-based composites, and their effect on the behaviour of the material was studied[40–46].

In this study, the effect of either partial, full, or excess replacement of standard quartz sand filler by waste from the production of silica bricks in MOC-based construction composites is studied. The influence of the ratio between the amount of matrix and the filler on the mechanical parameters is studied and described in detail. The proposed composites show an eco-friendly alternative to ordinary construction materials while utilizing an alternative filler that would otherwise end up landfilled.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Composite sample preparation

For the preparation of all composite samples, MgO powder (Penta s.r.o., Prague, Czech Republic) and $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Lach-Ner, s.r.o., Neratovice, Czech Republic) of p.a. purity, and tap water were used. For the reference sample (named **REF**) standard quartz sand (Filtrační písky, spol. s r.o., Chlum, Czech Republic) in three size fractions 0.0–0.5 (PG1), 0.5–1.0 (PG2), and 1.0–2.0 mm (PG3) in the weight ratio of 1:1:1 was used. For composite samples **SW50**, **SW100**, and **SW150**, waste from silica bricks production (RHI Magnesita Czech Republic a.s., Velké Opatovice, Czech Republic, termed **SW**) was used as a replacement of quartz sand fractions PG1 and PG2 in the amount of 50, 100, and 150 wt%, respectively. The silica bricks production process, during which SW is formed is described in detail in [28]. The weight proportions of the designed MOC-based composite mixtures are summarized in Table 1. For the REF, SW50, and SW100 composites, the mass ratio of filler to binder and the ratio of filler to total mix mass were similar, 1.1384 and 0.532, respectively. Sample WS150 had different ratios due to the higher filler content in the mix composition. In this case, we tried to add additional refractory waste to the original mix to verify if the original matrix is able to accumulate more waste in the form of filler to replace the silica sand of PG1 and PG2 fractions.

The stages of the experimental work are schemed in a flow chart in Fig. 1.

The composite mixtures were prepared using an automatic planetary mortar mixer. MgO powder and an aqueous solution of MgCl_2 were mixed for 30 s in a low-speed regime (140 rpm). Afterward, the mixing was stopped and the respective filler was added. The mixing continued for another 30 s at low speed, followed by 60 s in a high-speed regime (285 rpm). After that, the mixer bowl and paddle were scraped and then, the preparation process was completed by mixing for an additional 3 min at high speed. In this way, homogeneous and uniformly dispersed mixtures were obtained. These mixtures were poured into standard prismatic moulds (40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm). The samples were demoulded 24 h after casting and left in an air-conditioned laboratory at $T = 23 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $RH = 50 \pm 5 \%$. The curing conditions have a significant effect on the development of strength and other functional properties of MOC-based materials. Xu et al [47]. analyzed the influence of curing regimes on the mechanical properties of MOC-based composites. They showed that the introduction of high-temperature curing (in this case at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) can lead to significant improvement in the compressive strength of MOC-based composites compared to those subjected to ambient curing. However, prior to the application of high-temperature curing, ambient curing (at laboratory temperature of $23\text{--}25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) is required at an early stage. In the case of the above-mentioned study, 7 days of laboratory temperature curing followed by 21 days of $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ curing were applied. Nevertheless, the authors noted that the high-temperature curing had a negative effect on the water resistance of the composite studied and limited the formation and growth of phase 5. In this regard, ambient curing at $T = 23 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was used in our research.

2.2. Analytical methods and measurements

Before the preparation of the designed MOC-based composites, both raw fillers were subjected to multiple types of analyses in order to determine their phase and chemical composition, microstructure, morphology, particle size distribution, specific density, loose bulk density, and thermophysical parameters.

The hardened composite samples underwent experimental tests and analyses at the age of 28 days. These samples were subjected to several experimental tests and analyses that encompassed evaluating their phase and chemical composition, microstructure, morphology, basic physical, structural, mechanical, hygric, and thermal parameters.

To evaluate the particle size distribution standard sieve analysis was implemented using sieves with the following mesh sizes: 0.063, 0.125, 0.250, 0.500, 1.0, and 2.0 mm. For a more detailed study of the particle size among smaller size fractions of the fillers, laser diffraction (LD) was implemented. The phase composition was determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD), and the chemical composition was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Microstructure and morphology were studied using optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Specific density was determined using helium pycnometry. Loose bulk density was measured for uncompacted and fully compacted granular materials placed in a graduated cylinder. The samples were vacuum dried at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and their mass and volume were accurately determined. To determine the pore size distribution and pore structure parameters, mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP) was used. Among the thermal parameters of the used fillers, the thermal conductivity and the volumetric heat capacity were analyzed using a portable heat transfer analyzer equipped with a needle probe of an appropriate measuring range. Furthermore, continuous thermal decomposition was studied using simultaneous thermal analysis with a mass spectrometer (STA-MS).

Table 1
Weight proportions of designed composite mixtures ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$).

Composite	MgO	$\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_2O	SW	PG1	PG2	PG3
REF	403.0	406.7	252.3	-	403.0	403.0	403.0
SW50	385.1	388.6	241.1	385.1	192.5	192.5	385.1
SW100	383.4	386.9	240.0	766.8	-	-	383.4
SW150	327.7	330.8	205.2	983.3	-	-	327.7

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the activities done throughout the study.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Raw filler materials

Before the preparation of the designed MOC-based composite samples, the fillers were analyzed and compared to each other. As PG3 was used in all of the compositions, and the composite samples differed only in the content of SW, PG1, and PG2, all of the analyses were performed. Therefore, SW was compared to the mix of PG1 and PG2 (sample termed PG1 +PG2). This decision was based on the fine granularity of SW declared by the provider, which made it a suitable substitute only for these two size fractions of quartz sand.

The particle size distribution of SW and PG1 +PG2 blend obtained from sieve analysis is shown in Fig. 2a. The results obtained from LD are shown in Fig. 2b. These results support the decision to use SW as a partial replacement for PG1 and PG2 only, as its particle size distribution corresponded well to the particle size distributions of these two size fractions of the standardized filler.

The phase composition of the raw fillers was determined using XRD. Both fillers showed the presence of silicon oxide phases in different modifications. For the sample SW, it was cristobalite (ICDD 01–075–0923) and tridymite (ICDD 01–088–1535), the presence of which is caused by the thermal treatment of the original refractory bricks. For sample PG1 +PG2, silicon oxide in the form of quartz (ICDD 01–070–3755) was detected as the prevailing crystalline phase. Otherwise, no other phases or impurities were present in either of the filler materials. The diffraction patterns of the raw fillers are shown in Fig. 3.

The chemical composition of the two filler samples, SW and PG1 +PG2, was determined using XRF, recalculated to the content of oxides, and normalized (see Table 2). The remaining weight proportion was assigned to light elements, such as C, which cannot be detected through this analytical method. In addition, thermal treatment of SW in a furnace up to 1000°C was performed, where on weight decrease was obtained. This experiment proved that the content of moisture and light elements that can be oxidized (as well as carbonates) is negligible. Both samples were also studied using EDS, which provided elemental maps of the main elements present in these samples. The elemental maps are shown in Fig. 4. Both samples showed the presence of Si, O, C, and Al. Furthermore, the sample SW also contained a small amount of Ca. The quantity obtained from EDS is presented in Table 3, however, one must consider the lower precision of this measurement, as the obtained content of the individual elements is closely related to a very small area of the measured sample.

Fig. 2. Grain size curves of the used fillers obtained from sieve analysis (a) and LD (b).

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction patterns of samples SW and PG1 +PG2.

Table 2

Chemical composition of samples SW and PG1 +PG2 recalculated to oxides and normalized obtained from XRF.

Sample	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	K ₂ O	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃
	wt%					
SW	0.09	0.48	94.93	0.14	3.39	0.97
PG1 +PG2	-	0.02	99.66	0.03	0.01	0.28

Fig. 4. Elemental maps of samples SW (top) and PG1 +PG2 (bottom).

Table 3

Chemical composition of the studied areas of samples SW and PG1 +PG2 obtained from EDS.

Sample	C	O	Al	Si	Ca
	wt%				
SW	37.1	38.9	0.2	22.8	1.1
PG1 +PG2	9.0	49.2	0.3	41.5	-

The physical properties of the uncompacted and compacted fillers are presented in Table 4. The specific density and thus the bulk density were higher for sample PG1 +PG2 compared to SW. This corresponds well with the low porosity of the sand particles, which resulted in high heat transport and storage parameters of the designed composites (see Chapter 3.2). On the other hand, lighter SW showed much lower heat transport ability and almost similar heat storage capacity. This can be exploited in the design of materials that allow the accumulation of thermal energy, e.g. for building products enabling the reduction of excessive temperature fluctuations such as heat gains (overheating) and losses.

Table 4
Physical parameters of quartz sand and SW.

Compaction	Specific density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Loose bulk density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Volumetric heat capacity $\times 10^6$ ($\text{Jm}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Thermal diffusivity $\times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
PG1 +PG2					
Uncompacted	2647	1.658	0.413	1.572	0.263
Compacted		1.930	0.579	1.690	0.343
SW					
Uncompacted	2284	1.283	0.242	1.476	0.164
Compacted		1.507	0.367	1.565	0.235

3.2. MOC-based composites

After 28 days of curing, the prepared MOC-based composite samples (see Fig. 5, left) underwent a series of analytical tests and measurements. The fracture surface of the prepared specimens was studied using optical microscopy. The obtained micrographs (Fig. 5, right) show their close-packed defect-free structure, in which the filler grains of various sizes are homogeneously distributed. The replacement of sand with SW caused a minor discoloration of the specimens.

The phase composition of the prepared composite samples was determined using XRD. All of the prepared samples contained MOC Phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ICDD 04–014–8836), and one or more modifications of silicon oxide - quartz (ICDD 01–070–3755), cristobalite (ICDD 01–075–0923), and tridymite (01–088–1535) – coming from the two types of filler, as described above. The diffraction patterns of all the prepared samples are shown in Fig. 6.

The chemical composition of the composite samples was studied using EDS. Elemental maps are provided in Fig. 7. All samples contained O, Mg, Cl, Si, and C. The EDS elemental maps help to clearly distinguish the MOC matrix (areas with a high concentration of Mg, and Cl), and the filler particles (areas with high content of Si). The presence of carbon is caused by the surface reaction of the MOC matrix with atmospheric carbon dioxide, which results in the formation of a very small amount of a magnesium chlorocarbonate phase, as was described in our previous research [48]. The quantitative analysis performed using EDS provided the percentual content of each element present in the maps, the results are summarized in Table 5.

The microstructure of the prepared composite samples is shown in micrographs in Fig. 8. All samples show the presence of the typical needle-shaped MOC phase 5 crystals with lengths between 1 and 10 μm and width between 0.1 and 0.5 μm . It can be seen that the shape of the MOC needles differs between the reference, in which they are wider and shorter compared to the SW-containing samples. In those, the needles are thinner and sharper. This can be caused by the lower bulk density and higher open porosity of SW compared to the PG filler, due to which the SW filler helps to increase the crystallization rate, and its particles work as nucleation centres for MOC crystallization. All obtained micrographs show the compact structure of the prepared composites with no visible cracks or air bubbles. This contributes to overall high values of mechanical parameters obtained for all the compositions, and the corresponding values of basic physical, structural, and microstructural parameters presented further in the manuscript.

The structural parameters of the prepared composites are presented in Table 6. The incorporation of SW into composites decreased their bulk density and specific density, but no obvious relationship between these two structural parameters to the dosage of SW in composites was identified. Nevertheless, the obtained data are in good agreement with the lower loose bulk density and specific density of SW itself compared to silica sand. Only minor changes in porosity were observed for the SW-containing composites. A certain reduction in total open porosity values was noted for sample SW100; the decrease in porosity value was approximately 6 % compared to the reference composite sample REF with quartz sand as the only filler. The microstructural parameters, total pore volume, and average pore size were the lowest for sample SW150. The average pore size also decreased for sample SW50, which, together with the

Fig. 5. The prepared MOC-based composites (left) and OM micrographs of their fracture surface (right).

Fig. 6. X-ray diffraction patterns of samples REF, SW50, SW100, and SW150.

porosity values, can lead to the assumption of refinement of the porous structure by SW. On the other hand, sample SW50 exhibited the highest total pore volume, i.e. the highest volume of mercury intruded into the pores. Overall, the changes in physical, structural, and microstructural parameters after the replacement of sand with SW are not very significant, which is well supported by the SEM microstructural study presented in the micrographs above.

For a detailed analysis of the microstructure of the hardened composites, MIP was performed to obtain pore size distribution curves (Fig. 9) and volume fractions of pores of specific diameter ranges (Fig. 10). The highest volume of pores in the 1–10 nm diameter range was observed in the SW50 composite and, conversely, this material had the lowest proportion of pores that negatively affect mechanical strength. Sample SW150 had the highest proportion of capillary pores that allow water transport (pore diameter 100–1000 nm) and pores with diameter > 1000 nm, which cause deterioration of mechanical strength. The classification of pores and their effect on the hygric and mechanical performance of the investigated composites was carried out as introduced in [49,50].

The mechanical parameters of the investigated composites are shown in Fig. 11. The compressive strength of the materials with SW

Fig. 7. Elemental maps of samples REF, SW50, SW100, and SW150 obtained from EDS.

Table 5

Chemical composition of the studied areas of samples REF, SW50, SW100, and SW150 obtained from EDS.

Sample	Si	Mg	O	Cl	C
	wt%				
REF	34.8	10.9	39.6	6.2	8.4
SW50	9.4	25.8	43.2	13.8	7.8
SW100	9.1	26.7	40.3	16.0	7.8
SW150	16.5	21.4	43.3	11.5	7.4

was higher than that of sample REF and correlated well with the MIP data and refinement of the porous structure. The increase in compressive strength was 25.4 %, 19.9 %, and 6.3 % for SW50, SW100, and SW150, respectively. Such a high increase in compressive strength by using industrial waste is very promising for the development of low-carbon alternatives to PC-based construction materials. The flexural strength of the SW-modified materials remained almost unaffected (except for sample SW100), demonstrating that the filling effect (improvement in packing density) was the reason for the increase in compressive strength. Quantitatively, the f_{fl}/f_c ratio was high (0.30–0.38), which is the typical benefit of MOC-based materials[51]. The values of Young's modulus, which is a measure of stiffness, were reduced with the use of SW in composites, but they remained high enough to classify the studied composites as brittle materials. The brittleness of the composites was well apparent during their mechanical testing and loading up to the ultimate strength.

The water absorption coefficient determined in a free water uptake test is shown in Table 7. The lowest water uptake rate was observed for the samples SW50 and SW100 composites. The decrease in A_w values was 20.7 % and 18.3 % for SW50 and SW100, respectively. This was consistent with the pore volume fraction, i.e., the volume of capillary pores that allow liquid water transport. Similarly, the softening coefficient was greatly improved for these two composites as the water absorption was decelerated and limited, clearly demonstrating the contribution of the used SW to the performance and properties of the composites. The enhancement in softening coefficient, i.e. water resistance, was increased by 24.5 %, 11.3 %, and 2.1 % for samples SW50, SW100, and SW150, respectively.

Thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity were the measured thermophysical parameters. Quantitatively, the thermal conductivity value of reference REF was consistent with that presented by Xu et al[47]. The use of SW in the composition of the composites studied retarded the heat transport. This effect was attributed to the lower thermal conductivity of SW compared to the compacted quartz sand (see Table 4) and the reduced bulk density of the composites with SW. On the other hand, although the volumetric heat capacity of sand was slightly higher than that of SW, the volumetric heat capacity of SW-containing composites was

Fig. 8. SEM micrographs of samples REF, SW50, SW100, and SW150.

Table 6

Basic physical, structural and microstructural parameters and their expanded combined uncertainties.

Composite	Bulk density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Specific density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Porosity (%)	Total pore volume ($\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	Average pore size (nm)
REF	2008 ± 28	2271 ± 27	11.6 ± 0.2	0.0880	44.3
SW50	1921 ± 27	2171 ± 26	11.5 ± 0.2	0.0945	39.6
SW100	1923 ± 27	2159 ± 26	10.9 ± 0.2	0.0840	42.3
SW150	1927 ± 27	2175 ± 26	11.4 ± 0.2	0.0793	39.4

Fig. 9. Pore size distribution.

Fig. 10. Volume of pores of a specific pore diameter.

higher, demonstrating their self-passive heat storage capacity. In this case, the refinement of the porous structure of the composites with SW was the cause of the increased heat storage capacity which overcame the effect of the heat storage capacity of SW itself.

The thermal decomposition of the prepared composite samples was studied using STA-MS. The samples were heated up to $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a dynamic air atmosphere. During this process, the full decomposition of MOC Phase 5, which was described in our previous work [48], took place. The decomposition consisted of the release of crystalline water in the form of water vapor between 100 and $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$,

Fig. 11. Compressive strength, flexural strength and dynamic Young's modulus.

Table 7

Hygric, thermal and durability parameters including their expanded combined uncertainties.

Composite	Water absorption coefficient $\times 10^{-3}(\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1/2})$	Thermal conductivity $(\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1})$	Volumetric heat capacity $(\text{MJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1})$	Softening coefficient (-)
REF	8.2 ± 2	2.02 ± 0.04	1.91 ± 0.04	0.755 ± 0.015
SW50	6.5 ± 1	1.91 ± 0.04	1.99 ± 0.04	0.940 ± 0.019
SW100	6.7 ± 2	1.74 ± 0.04	1.95 ± 0.04	0.833 ± 0.017
SW150	8.9 ± 2	1.81 ± 0.04	1.98 ± 0.04	0.739 ± 0.015

Fig. 12. STA-MS curves of sample REF.

and a small amount of gaseous HCl around 460 °C. The DTA, TG, and MS curves obtained from this analysis are shown in Figs. 12–15. The remaining content of the solid phase, which can be presumed to be pure MgO and SiO₂ was 78.50, 75.00, 76.53, and 80.31 wt% for REF, SW50, SW100, and SW150, respectively.

4. Conclusions

This research was focused on the substitution of quartz sand filler with silicate refractory brick waste (SW) in magnesium oxychloride-based composite materials. This approach will reduce production costs by using waste raw materials in newly developed

Fig. 13. STA-MS curves of sample SW50.

Fig. 14. STA-MS curves of sample SW100.

Fig. 15. STA-MS curves of sample SW150.

composites. It was proved that such replacement significantly improved material properties. The following conclusions were drawn based on the obtained results.

- i) Sample SW150 yielded a compressive strength of 85.9 MPa, while for sample SW100 it was 96.9 MPa, which shows an increase of 6.3 % and 19.9 %, respectively, compared to the reference. Sample SW50 showed even higher values: compressive strength reached 101.3 MPa, which presents a 25.4 % increase.
- ii) All prepared composites exhibited remarkable flexural strength values exceeding 30 MPa. The flexural/compressive strength ratio varied from 0.30 to 0.38, which is much higher as compared to that of conventional PC concrete.
- iii) Microstructural analysis indicated a significant reduction in the share of capillary pores (with diameters between 100 and 1000 nm), which are typically responsible for water-induced damage in MOC-based composites. This resulted in the lower water absorption coefficient of SW50 and SW100 samples and their improved softening coefficient, which was 94.0 % and 83.3 %, respectively.
- iv) The thermal conductivity of SW reduced the ability of the composites to transfer heat. Compared to the reference composite, the reduction in thermal conductivity was 5.4 %, 13.9 %, and 10.4 % for SW50, WS100, and SW150.
- v) The overall heat storage capacity of the composites remained high and varied from 1.91 to 1.98 MJ·m⁻³·K⁻¹.

The determined physical parameters of the tested MOC-based composites with SW used in the form of filler make them a promising sustainable alternative to PC-based materials applicable in multiple branches of the construction industry, such as flooring, preshaped or prefabricated construction elements, facing panels, or lining. The excellent mechanical resistance of the developed materials can also be exploited in load-bearing structures, where the risk of moisture-induced damage is eliminated. It must be said, that the utilized waste filler is of a rather local character, however, similar spent refractories can be found globally, and the proposed solution for their reuse as filler in MOC-based composites is possible and could be fully exploited and researched on not only in future research, but also in all of the above-mentioned industrial applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zbyšek Pavlík: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Michal Lojka:** Investigation, Data curation. **Oskar Chmel:** Investigation, Data curation. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martina Záleská:** Investigation, Data curation. **Adam Pivák:** Investigation, Data curation. **Milena Pavlíková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The raw data presented in this paper is accessible through the following DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10908602.

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